

Research Article

Analysis of the Implementation of Islamic Boarding School Culture to Strengthen the Religious and Independent Character of Assalam Integrated Vocational School Students, Durenan, Trenggalek Regency

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to analyze the application of Islamic boarding school culture in order to strengthen the religious and independent character of the students of SMK Terpadu Assalam Durenan. This research is a qualitative descriptive research. This research is located in Pondok Pesantren SMK Terpadu Assalam Durenan. Determination of the subject of this research is carried out purposively. Data collection techniques were carried out by 1) observation, 2) interviews, 3) documentation. Data collection techniques used the techniques of 1) data collection, 2) data reduction, 3) data presentation, 4) drawing conclusions. The results showed that strengthening the religious character of students through religious activities such as the habit of praying together, reading the Koran, etc. Strengthening the independent character of students is through habituation carried out by students and entrepreneurship programs to honor students' abilities in the field of entrepreneurship. Supporting factors for strengthening the religious character and independent character of students are the supportive environment of the Islamic boarding school and complete infrastructure. While the inhibiting factors from strengthening the religious and independent character of students, namely the discipline and enthusiasm of students in participating in activities are still lacking, because they still have to adapt to the new environment. The solution in overcoming obstacles is that the administrators must be more firm in punishing students who do not obey the rules and students must also increase their willingness to learn.

Keywords: Student, Religious Character, Independent Character, Islamic Boarding School Culture.

Introduction

Education essentially aims to provide knowledge to each individual in order to help humans to become smart and have good character. The process in education of making people smart and can be done by providing quality learning, while the formation of good character seems more difficult because of the many external influences that can influence the character of each individual which results in moral problems that have not yet been resolved. It is well proven that there are still many violations occurring in society. The reality of this acute moral problem then places the implementation of character education as an important thing to overcome these character problems (Depiyanti, 2014: 134).

Character education is very important to be taught to students, because character education is education that instills and develops noble character which is very important for all students to have and can be practiced to create individuals with good character (Wibowo, 2012: 18). Strengthening character education in this era is very necessary and this can start from the first environment, namely the family, school and community. One of the character values that needs to be developed is religious character. Religious character formation is carried out throughout life because religious values influence other character values. Moreover, in this era, controlling children is very difficult to do, because with advances in technology, including the existence of cell phones, children have their own world that no one else can enter. The task of parents is to provide a good understanding of how to use cell phones properly and beneficial. Apart from that, independent character also really needs to be developed considering that nowadays many children are spoiled and always depend on their parents. Through strengthening character education, it is hoped that a

child will be able to independently increase knowledge, study and personalize character values so that they can be realized in everyday life. Education at the educational unit level leads to the formation of school culture, namely the values that underlie behavior, traditions and daily habits (Mulyasa, 2012: 9).

Citizenship education is one of the pillars of character formation and national identity, because citizenship education has the aim of educating citizens to become good citizens and citizens who have intelligence (smart citizens) to face current developments. Character education in citizenship education learning is a solution to revitalize the role of citizenship as a scientific discipline which is a tool for developing the character of students. Citizenship education is a subject whose material content has character values which can help to integrate the concept of character education (Zulfikar and Dewi, 2021: 114).

Citizenship education and character education are related to each other, because the aim of both is to shape the character of citizens themselves, therefore character education can be implemented through citizenship education. If the value of character education is implemented through citizenship education, then it can be said that the character values for citizenship education include basic character values and main character values. The main character values of citizenship education are to create students who are: religious, honest, intelligent, independent, tough, democratic and caring. Meanwhile, the main character values of citizenship education are to create students who have a nationalist spirit, obey the rules, respect differences, have an awareness of the rights and obligations of themselves and others, are responsible, think logically, critically, creatively and innovatively, and are independent. These main character values can be developed more widely, in an effort to strengthen the function of citizenship education as character education (Juliardi, 2015: 124).

Vocational high school (SMK) is an educational institution that has the responsibility to produce human resources who have abilities, skills and expertise so that graduates can develop their abilities when they later enter the world of education (Firdausi and Barnawi, 2012: 13). Islamic boarding schools have various important roles in improving the quality of human resources. As is generally known, Islamic boarding schools do not only provide technical knowledge and skills, but what is much more important is instilling moral and religious values which serve as a way of life for a peaceful life. Islamic boarding schools are used as agents of change as intermediary institutions which are expected to act as dynamists and catalysts for empowering human resources, driving development in all fields, as well as developing science and technology in welcoming the global era (Usman, 2013: 114).

Islamic boarding school-based schools are an educational model that integrates a combination of the education system held in schools and the education system held in Islamic boarding schools through educational dimensions, namely the possession of a strong foundation of religious morality, mastery of science and technology, as well as possessing and mastering forms of skills-work skills that will support their life after completing their education. It is hoped that students who study at Islamic boarding school-based formal educational institutions will be able to have a combination of knowledge combined with religious knowledge (Wahid and Santoso, 2021: 98).

Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School is a formal vocational education institution based on Islamic boarding schools managed by the PPT NU Assalam Trenggalek foundation. Students at Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School are divided into 2 parts, namely students who do not live in Islamic boarding schools and students who live in Islamic boarding schools. Learning for students who board (live) in Islamic boarding schools is by combining learning in formal schools with learning like in Islamic boarding schools. School starts from morning until afternoon, followed by Koran activities. Not all students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School have boarded before, therefore the management has the task of making all students able to quickly adapt to their new environment at the boarding school. With the presence of students who have never previously received education at an Islamic boarding school, this results in the students' enthusiasm for participating in activities being a little low, because they have to get used to taking part in the existing activities first, besides that it also affects the value of the students' independence because they are used to living at home with other people. Their parents also influence the activeness of students in activities, such as the low level of awareness of students participating in activities at Islamic boarding schools (Archives/Islamic Boarding School/Profile, 5/9/20).

Apart from school learning activities, religious activities and so on, there are also other activities such as extra-curricular activities, training which aims to support the abilities of Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School students' abilities. Assalam Durenan Trenggalek Integrated Vocational

School is a new school that was born in 2016 and has now become the largest Islamic boarding school-based vocational school in Trenggalek Regency.

The Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School teaches students to be able to live simply, independently according to the conditions in the Islamic boarding school, so that students can be serious about studying, because every student, whether from affluent or less fortunate families, can experience the same life at the boarding school. At the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School, they come from different regions, this is what adds to their sense of kinship. From different backgrounds and regions, they can gather as a family at the Islamic boarding school (Archive/ Islamic Boarding School/Learning, 5/9/20).

Students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School come from various areas in Trenggalek district and surrounding areas, not all of the students have received Islamic boarding school education before, many students who were previously students from public schools that were not based on Islamic boarding schools had to adapt from the start so that they can carry out activities at the Islamic boarding school. Religious cultivation in students is an important thing to implement because there are still many students who previously did not come from Islamic boarding school-based schools and there are students who come from Islamic boarding schools but still lack religious knowledge. The flagship program of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School is about technology which is focused on the school's departments and entrepreneurship which is found in activities at the Islamic boarding school, such as sandal production activities and vocational school uniform production activities.

Research Methods

Types and Research Approaches

This research is a qualitative descriptive research. The choice of a qualitative descriptive approach was based on a study of the application of Islamic boarding school culture which requires a direct study of the lives of students in Islamic boarding schools. The descriptions described are the main experiences of several people who experienced the incident or participated in research activities. Qualitative descriptive research in the form of phenomenology requires a strong philosophical basis from in-depth interviews (Creswell, 2016: 18-19). Qualitative research is methods for exploring and understanding meaning by a number of individuals or groups of people which are ascribed to social or humanitarian problems (Creswell, 2016: 4).

The aim of this research is to provide information in the form of descriptive data regarding strengthening the religious character and independent character of students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School. This method is used because it examines current problems, especially regarding aspects of strengthening the religious character and independent character of students.

Time and Place of Research

The research time starts from the proposal preparation process to carrying out the research. This research was carried out from August 2020 to September 2021. The location chosen for this research was the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School which is located at Karangrejo Hamlet, Sumbergayam Village, Durenan District, Trenggalek Regency, East Java.

Data Source

The data sources in this research are primary data and secondary data. The research sample in this study is representative of the elements at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School, consisting of caregivers, principals, heads of Madrasah Diniyah, management representatives, class X student representatives, class XI student representatives, and class XII student representatives.

Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

In this research, data collection uses observation, interviews and documentation. Meanwhile, data collection instruments use observation guidelines, interview guidelines and documentation guidelines.

Data Validity

The validity of the data in this research uses source triangulation and technical triangulation.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis process in this research has several components, namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation, drawing conclusions.

Results and Discussion

1. Implementation of the Culture of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School to Strengthen the Religious Character of the Students

Furkan (2013: 123-124) states that the models and methods for character formation are as follows:

a) Habituation

Habit is something that is deliberately done repeatedly so that something becomes a habit. Habituation usually has experience at its core, what gets used to is something that is practiced. Habit places humans as something special, which can save strength because it will become an inherent and spontaneous habit, so that strength can be used for various activities in every job, and other activities.

b) School Routine Activities

Routine school activities are activities carried out by school members continuously and consistently at school, such as flag ceremonies, Friday prayers together, reading Yasin together, praying before and after class, saying hello and greetings when meeting among school members, checking body hygiene (hooves, ears and hair).

c) Environmental Conditioning

Environmental conditioning is an activity carried out intentionally or unintentionally or an activity that is specifically conditioned in such a way by providing physical school facilities to support the implementation of character education through school culture.

Strengthening the religious character of students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School. In general, if seen from the discipline of the students in participating in religious activities at the Islamic boarding school, the students are very enthusiastic in participating in all activities carried out by the Islamic boarding school. This can happen with hard work and patience from all elements in the Islamic boarding school in order to accustom the students to be able to be steadfast in carrying out all the activities in the Islamic boarding school. The method used is by always emphasizing discipline in the students, that is, the administrators always wake up and remind the students to immediately rush to the place where the activity is taking place and the ustad is ready to start the activity. It takes a lot of patience to improve student discipline because many students have never boarded before so they are still not used to the activities carried out in Islamic boarding schools. The exemplary attitude of the ustad, kiai, and administrators will encourage students to carry out religious activities such as giving charity, doing good deeds, speaking politely. At the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School, students from the start have been introduced to and familiarized with religious activities such as madrasah diniyah, sorogan Al Qur'an, reciting the yellow book and there are qiyamul lail activities so that they can learn and improve their skills in religious knowledge. The method of giving stories (qashash), the method of parables (amtsal), and the method of giving gifts (tsawab) and punishment (iqlab).

Religious activities at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School begin with qiyamul lail which is carried out before dawn. This activity is not required for all students considering that most of the students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School have never received Islamic boarding school education and the Islamic boarding school also provides a little leeway considering that the age of the students are still teenagers and if on Mondays and Thursdays they continue to eat sahur to carry out the Monday and Thursday fast. Followed by congregational prayers at dawn, wiridan and practices (yasin, tahlil, istighosah together, practice of surah wakingah, surah ar rahman, and surah al mulk) which are rotated throughout the week. Then the students prepare to go to vocational school, at 07.00-13.00 vocational school learning takes place and the congregation prays midday prayers together with all vocational school students, both those who live in Islamic boarding schools and students who do not live in Islamic boarding schools. Then there is a break from school at 13.00 until the Asr prayer congregation (here the Asr prayer congregation is around 16.00), after the Asr prayer congregation there is a yellow book reading activity, until sunset comes and all the students and ustad perform the Maghrib congregational prayer together. The same after the congregation prays the evening prayer; students are required to recite the Koran.

Religious activities at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School have an influence on strengthening the religiousness of the students because at the Islamic boarding school the students are taught about habits in religious activities, good manners and the students are given exemplary examples from the ustad, kiai and administrators in their daily lives. It is hoped that the habits implemented

will make students accustomed (istiqomah) to carrying out all activities, especially religious activities, in order to increase the religiousness of students. The sources of religious values that apply in human life are classified into 2 types, namely: Divine values (values related to divinity) and Insaniyah values (values related to humans) (Zayadi, 2011: 73).

Islamic boarding schools have their own way of teaching morals, etiquette, behavior and manners towards their students, Islamic boarding schools regulate the rules regarding the manners, and manners of a student towards the teacher, students towards other students, students towards the teacher's family, even Islamic boarding schools, It also regulates the manners of a student with his textbooks or books, how to honor and respect a teacher, friends and his books. In line with character education which is being promoted by the government, the world of Islamic education has long before introduced the concept of education which not only pays attention to cognitive aspects, but also places more emphasis on building the character and morals of students through adab education, because adab is a character that must be emphasized. Firstly, to the students, remember that if a person with knowledge does not have manners, he will not be able to practice his knowledge well (Nurdin, 2015: 163). The character values that are instilled at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School because the school is based on Islamic boarding schools are the characters that are emphasized, namely manners and religious character itself. Because etiquette is the most important thing that must be possessed by all individuals, especially students, because if someone who is knowledgeable does not have good etiquette then the knowledge they have cannot be useful to other people, they will feel that they are the smartest and will always show off their arrogance. Apart from that, the expected religious value is students' devotion to Allah SWT.

2. Implementation of the Culture of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School to Strengthen the Independent Character of Students

The character of independence can be accustomed to in everyday life, but it cannot be separated from a good moral attitude (Gleeson and O'Flaherty, 2016:49). The independent character of the students of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School can be seen from the strategy when implementing the rules, regulations and policies that are applied to the students' daily lives, thanks to the efforts made by the management and other elements of the Islamic boarding school which provide learning to the students regarding independence which is also very beneficial for strengthening the independent character of students. Because in Islamic boarding schools the students are stressed to be able to do everything themselves, Islamic boarding schools also facilitate activities that can support the students, such as the production of vocational school uniforms for female students and the production of sandals and mug souvenirs for male students which aims to increase the students' skills which can be useful when the students have graduated from school. Compared to other students who do not go to boarding school, it is very far away because in Islamic boarding schools, students are taught not to depend on their parents, as is usually done at home.

Education equips students not only to know, but to be skilled at doing or doing something so as to produce something meaningful for life. In line with the soft skills possessed by students, they need to be equipped with reliable entrepreneurial skills education. This is in line with strengthening the independence of Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School students' independence through an entrepreneurship program, namely the production of vocational school uniforms for female students and the production of sandals, mugs and screen printing for male students which can foster students' independence. (Department of Religion, 2005:10).

The strategy of Islamic boarding schools in fostering the independence of students is 1) students are educated to do all their own activities such as washing clothes, washing dishes, helping to cook and so on themselves, unlike when they are at home there are parents who are always beside the students. 2) Entrepreneurial activities that are beneficial for students, such as the production of vocational school uniforms for female students as well as the production of sandals and mug souvenirs, screen printing for male students. Because the Islamic boarding school also accepts orders, the students are also taught direct manufacturing practices and if there is an order then the results of the production that the students make will be counted and given in exchange for sweat as pocket money for the students. In practice, the students are accompanied by a team of experts in their respective fields to support the students' ability to quickly master the entrepreneurship program. There are many benefits from the entrepreneurship program held at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School, such as students having new abilities in terms of entrepreneurship and this can be one of the answers after they graduate because the entrepreneurship program does not only focus on production but also focuses on knowledge. Marketing is

very necessary for entrepreneurs. Apart from that, Islamic boarding schools also benefit from the existence of this entrepreneurship program, namely that Islamic boarding schools have new sources of funds in their management and become a positive value in gaining public trust so that it will increase parents' interest in enrolling their children in Islamic boarding schools.

There are benefits to be gained from student empowerment activities (entrepreneurship), namely: 1) The students will be more independent and more confident, this is because apart from having religious knowledge that will be conveyed to the community, the alumni also have the provisions to meet the needs of the world (economic) independently or for economic needs no longer depending on others. 2) Islamic boarding schools will be more independent and develop quickly, because the source of funds which until now only relied on students and donors, now has a new source of funds. 3) Islamic boarding schools will gain more trust from the community, thereby increasing parents' interest in enrolling their children in Islamic boarding schools (Ismail, 2016: 60). The activities carried out in Islamic boarding schools greatly influence the independence of students, because in educating students to be able to develop their own potential, an individual must be accustomed to being able to do everything themselves, and students are accustomed to improving their abilities, such as with the entrepreneurship program in Islamic boarding schools, namely production of vocational school uniforms for female students as well as production of sandals, mug souvenirs and screen printing for male students. The hope is that from an early age the students will have the skills and experience in entrepreneurship so that later, after the students graduate, they will not be surprised and will be able to develop the knowledge they have gained at the Islamic boarding school.

3. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors for Strengthening the Religious Character and Independent Character of Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School Students

The supporting factor for strengthening the religious character and independent character of students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School is that the Islamic boarding school environment really supports the students' learning process, because the surrounding environment at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School is relatively quiet because it is not on the main route, apart from that, the community around the Islamic boarding school very religious in practicing his religion as evidenced by his lively activities at the Baiturrahman Mosque which is also the center for religious education for students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School. Apart from that, complete facilities and infrastructure are one of the supporting factors in the success of education. Places of worship, laboratories, tools and so on are very complete, making it easier for students to be able to understand what is being taught, as is the case with the entrepreneurship program, at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School, there are sandal making machines, souvenir mugs, sewing machines and so on.

Motivations from within students that influence students' behavior include not being able to adapt, not being able to carry out the rules, not having clear goals or ideals and a feeling of hatred towards those who enforce discipline. The first motivation is influenced by the students' inability to adapt to the dormitory environment. This happens a lot to new students who are not used to living independently in an Islamic boarding school environment. So students need time to be able to carry out all existing disciplinary rules. (Baqi *et al.*, 2017: 83). The inhibiting factors for strengthening the religious character and independent character of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School students are the minimal number of administrators and the students themselves, because after research there are still students (especially new students) who still need adaptation in participating in existing activities, as well as the enthusiasm of the students also a little less. Even though there is a lot of knowledge that students can gain at Islamic boarding schools, apart from general knowledge at vocational schools, there is also religious knowledge which is very useful when they graduate from Islamic boarding schools.

The strategy implemented by the caregivers and administrators of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School of Islamic Boarding School to strengthen the religious character of the students is improving the manners of the students, because good manners and being diligent in carrying out religious activities are the main things that the students must have in order to achieve success. Several strategies are implemented to strengthen the religious character of students, namely:

a) Making a Routine Schedule of Activities

At the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School, students must take part in all activities at the Islamic boarding school according to a predetermined schedule. Having a routine schedule of activities makes it easier for administrators to organize the students so that the students can be orderly in

participating in all activities at the Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School. Assalam Durenan, as well as to familiarize students with participating in all existing activities according to their schedule. Religious activities at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School include madrasah diniyah, sorogan Al Qur'an, recitation of the yellow book, qiyamul lail and so on.

b) Direct Approach to Students

The approach taken by all elements in the Islamic boarding school aims to give special attention to the students so that the students feel close to the administrators, kiai, ustad and so on to make it easier to control the students in their daily activities. As well as to minimize students who do not feel at home in the boarding school with a more approach and also to increase the awareness of students to follow all the activities and regulations in the Islamic boarding school.

c) Exemplary Attitude and Advice

The exemplary attitude of kiai, ustad, administrators and so on will encourage students to imitate the good deeds and words that have been exemplified by kiai, ustad and administrators while they are at the Islamic boarding school and follow all the advice that has been given.

d) Giving Rewards and Punishments

It is very necessary to give gifts to students in order to increase the enthusiasm of students to be active in the daily activities carried out by students. The assessment given is by observing the students' daily lives both when the students are at the Islamic boarding school, at school, or also when learning activities are taking place. Apart from that, punishment for students is also needed to provide learning and a slight deterrent effect to students who do not want to obey the rules given to students. The punishment given is simply to provide a deterrent effect and no physical punishment is carried out on students. The type of punishment is as follows: ordering students to clean the bathroom, sweep the yard and other punishments.

e) Material about the Stories of the Characters and Parables

The material provided by the ustad during religious learning at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School is exemplifying the stories of prophets and other religious figures so that they become role models that the students can emulate, as well as learning by providing parables to make it easier for the students to understand the material given by the ustad.

4. Solutions Used to Deal with Obstacles that Occur in the Process of Strengthening the Religious Character and Independent Character of Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School Students

In improving the process of strengthening religious character and independent character, all elements must be involved in the process, such as caregivers, ustadz, administrators, and the students themselves. In the process there are regulations which will have to be obeyed by all elements of the Islamic boarding school, especially the students themselves. If the regulations can be obeyed then everything that is the goal of learning will run according to what is expected so that the learning process will run well and correct. The solution used to deal with obstacles that occur among students is that administrators must be more assertive in providing direction to students regarding the importance of learning and the knowledge they can gain at Islamic boarding schools. Apart from that, students must also be more aware of the importance of the knowledge they can gain at Islamic boarding schools and students must be able to divide their time between activities at Islamic boarding schools and their study time. Because actually in Islamic boarding schools there is also some free time that students can use for studying. The administrator must actively and continuously strive to play a smaller role, gradually developing self-control and self-direction in the students. Strategies to achieve the goal of developing Islamic boarding schools include, among other things, through the example of their caregivers, then through advice, as well as guidance and punishment (ta'zir) or rewards (Musdhaqiron, 2017:33).

Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclusions

Based on the research results and discussions that have been presented, several conclusions can be put forward as follows.

- 1) The process of strengthening the religious character of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School students' religious character is going well, as evidenced by the evaluation carried out, namely that in religious activities the students are very enthusiastic and active in participating in activities as evidenced by the attendance of the students. Students in Islamic boarding

schools must be able to divide their time between studying, school and activities at the Islamic boarding school. Activities carried out at the Assalam Integrated Vocational School of Islamic Boarding School include congregational prayers, Koran recitation activities, madrasah diniyah and so on which are carried out regularly. In Islam an individual who frequently participating in religious activities such as going to recitations, religious lectures and so on can motivate and trigger the growth of religion in him.

- 2) The process of strengthening the independent character of students at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School is going well, as evidenced by the daily activities of the students, such as during entrepreneurial activities and during other activities. Students must be able to do all their own needs, because students in Islamic boarding schools are far from their parents. One of the goals of students in Islamic boarding schools is so that students are able to live independently without help from other people, including their parents. Apart from that, there are activities that can increase the independence of students, especially with entrepreneurship programs that can increase their knowledge, such as the production of vocational school uniforms (sewing), the production of sandals and mug souvenirs.
- 3) Supporting factors in strengthening the religious character and independent character of the students of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School, namely the environment around the boarding school which is very supportive in the learning process as well as complete facilities and infrastructure, making it easier for the students to study and practice what they have learned. The inhibiting factors in strengthening the religious character and independent character of students are the minimal number of administrators and there are still many students, especially new students, who lack discipline in participating in activities carried out by Islamic boarding schools, and there are still students who complain about dividing their study time with existing activities due to the limited number of boarding school administrators, but in general this can be minimized.
- 4) The solution faced in order to deal with the obstacles that occur is that administrators must be more assertive in providing direction to students regarding the importance of learning and the knowledge that students will gain while at the Islamic boarding school, students must also be able to divide their time between activities at the Islamic boarding school and their learning activities and comply with every regulation that exists at the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational School Islamic Boarding School.

Suggestions

Referring to the research results, discussions and conclusions regarding strengthening the religious and independent character of the Assalam Durenan Integrated Vocational Islamic Boarding School students, as well as based on the aims and uses of the research, there are several suggestions that the researcher would like to convey, including the following:

- 1) Strengthening the religious and independent character of students requires good cooperation between kiai, ustad, administrators, students and openness to each other.
- 2) To see how big the religious and independent character of the students is, it is necessary to carry out regular reviews in order to further strengthen the religious and independent character of the students.
- 3) Considering the small number of administrators, the administrators have to work extra hard and always know what the students are complaining about and immediately provide the best solution for everyone.
- 4) Adding a number of administrators so they can focus more on monitoring every activity of the students.
- 5) Students must be able to be active in conveying suggestions which can later become learning input for Islamic boarding school elements in the future.
- 6) Evaluation in all matters including activities must be carried out routinely every month. So that if something undesirable happens, it can immediately appear and be resolved immediately.

Declarations

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